

THE COMPLEX PROBLEM OF FREE AND OPEN INDO-PACIFIC INITIATIVE: JAPAN'S ROLE IN DEFENDING THE REGION

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SUMMARY

This *Policy Brief* aims to explore the impact of the FOIP: *Free and Open Indo-Pacific initiative* in the Indo-Pacific region. Through an analytical and comparative methodology, we propose to analyze the various points of view of the initiative, with an emphasis on the role of Japan in consolidating a vision that aligns with its interests. The creation of an initiative presupposes that there is an ability to take action independently to achieve a goal, but in the case of FOIP, we have a complex situation that involves historical-cultural and socioeconomic ties that condition and limits certain states to take their own initiative. Japan as the main catalyst for the initiative, emerges as a case study presenting itself as the largest ally of the U.S. *but maintaining its status as a dynamic* of regional policies in the Indo-Pacific region.

BACKGROUND

The Indo-Pacific region is one of the most important regions in the world in the face of the strategic role it plays in global markets and is one of the most important hubs in terms of trade and exchange of goods/products. In the face of escalating tensions in the region, the FOIP (*Free and Open Indo Pacific*) initiative is created in order to try to regularize and protect regional and interregional trade.

FOIP was created in 2017 by the Trump administration in a clear attempt to contain China's economic growth in the Region by allowing free movement of goods and products in *China's commercial modus operandi*. In the spotlight is Japan, which throughout the Abe administration is trying to solidify ties with the U.S. and its partners in the region, and in 2007 the QUAD is creating quad for the growth of Japan's influence in the region over China. FOIP is a regional project to compete with China's regional project, *China's Belt Road Initiative* (1). The academic debate questions the very reasons for the creation where I can ascertain two options: a) Initiative for the solidification of the liberal order in the Indo-Pacific or b) A response from the Japanese government itself to its biggest competitor in the region.

In order to analyze the data, I tried to deepen the dynamics from the Japanese point of view by following my diplomatic statement.

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The Japanese Ministry of Foreign Affairs clarifies the purposes of its initiative in *its Diplomatic Bluebook 2019* with the following objectives:

- The promotion and solidification of the rule of law, freedom of navigation, free trade, etc.
- The pursuit of economic prosperity through the improvement of connectivity, including through the development of quality infrastructure according to international standards.
- The commitment to peace and stability that includes assistance for maritime law enforcement training, cooperation in areas such as disaster risk reduction and non-proliferation (2).

To a large extent the first two goals are more aligned with U.S. economic interests that directly benefit from the enforcement and legislation of navigation rights evidenced at the QUAD meeting by the American side where President Joe Biden proclaims "*The future of each of our nations-and indeed the world- depends on a free Indo-Pacific enduring and flourishing in the decades ahead*" (3).

The Japanese government realizes that it needs to captivate U.S. economic interest to continue investing in the region and promotes dialogue between the closest states in order to maintain the U.S. military presence in the region. For this reason, the third objective is where there is the greatest concern on the part of the Japanese government that wants to reconcile American interests with its regional claims in order to become more independent in the military fora. In this way Japan will make up for the US gap in the region with its economic might and investments in the ASEAN countries and the US would provide the necessary support to deter any military attempt by China or North Korea on Japanese territory, in particular attention to *the Senkaku islands disputed* between Tokyo and Beijing.

One of the reasons for the Japanese government's lack of deterrent power is that the country adopts a pacifist position with regard to its armed forces, and the army itself is still limited by post-war treaties with the US, and all the nuclear trauma that influences Japanese public opinion in situations involving nuclear technology. After the bombings of Hiroshima and Nagasaki, Japan adopted the policy known as the Three *Non-Nuclear Principles*, preventing Japan from possessing, manufacturing or introducing nuclear weapons into its territory. The public opinion of the country is so adverse to any nuclear initiatives in its country that despite Japan's energy dependence, only 18.4% of the population is in favour of the use of nuclear technology for energy creation areas (4). The topic is *taboo* in Japanese politics, further worsening after the Fukushima nuclear disaster in 2011. However, in the face of the developments of the war in Europe, former Japanese Prime Minister Shinzo Abe begins to warn of the military weakness of Japan, which is dependent on *the American nuclear umbrella*.

RESULTS

With the Kishida administration, there has been an advance and continuation of its forerunner Abe in strengthening Japanese security, including the allocation of an additional 1% of GDP (an increase of about US\$37 billion) related to defense-related expenditures, which may include new types of weaponry and military technology (5). This increase paves the way for Japan to manufacture nuclear weapons. There is already the technology needed to create nuclear warheads, only being conditioned due to lack of

political will and the resistance created by public opinion, which will certainly change if the risks of the conflict are imminent. While this is the most drastic measure, the biggest focus is on how to solidify alliances at regional and interregional level in order to preserve peace.

The creation of quad despite being a start is far from effective as an alliance, and so the Japanese government's strategy is to try to establish common points between QUAD and FOIP to strengthen its defensive position in the region (6). Although academic debate focuses on the most contemporary issues, we should also highlight the historical role that the Regions of the Indo-Pacific have and that affect the very survival of the region's initiatives. Sino-Japanese relations have a tremendous impact on the Indo-Pacific region resembling the relations that Franco Germanic (7) to the extent that they are largely responsible for the development of the region where they share a past of disputes and alliances alternately. Japanese diplomacy itself after the World War has been forced to maintain strictly commercial ties with other Asian peoples due to lack of political interest in the countries victims of Japanese imperialism (8), including China, which emerges as one of the obstacles to cooperation in the region.

The influence of the two states is the main reason for there being sudden stops in advancing the initiatives and that by supporting the BRI or FOIP will cause repercussions on the side of each party. An example case is that of South Korea, which although it is more aligned with the liberal order, has as its main trading partner China with exports that reach 25% (9). This dependence on Chinese trade requires caution on the part of the South Korean government when approving certain economic and political decisions. We can also question whether the most effective strategy will be to contain the entire region around China in order to impede its economic power, which will lead to repercussions that will directly impact global trade and weaknesses in Asian security, especially the case of Taiwan.

The escalation of tensions between Washington and Beijing over the Taiwan issue, China's non-alignment in support of Ukraine and the diplomatic distancing of both states, increasingly contribute to a rift between the liberal order and the Chinese area of influence. The latest u.S.-China officials even carry two messages, one from the White House and one from the top U.S. military, trying at all costs to prevent an escalation of the conflict. In this way, the US receives criticism for its interests in the region, regardless of the negative results it causes to the region. In this sense, Japan is in the ideal geostrategic position to be a stabilizing actor in the region, achieving the security it needs and maintaining its economic impact in the region, being the reference economy for the ASEAN countries. One of the evidence for Japan to become a stabilizing actor emerges *at the Japan-China Summit* held on November 17, 2022, which normalized diplomatic relations between both states (10). The U.S. fails to capture the multiple vicissitudes of regional dynamics, it makes room for Japan to consolidate its position by increasingly taking a key role in bringing the FOIP initiative from paper to reality.

The economic path is one of the major points preventing the scale of global conflicts in the Asia Pacific region and by analyzing the history of japan's post-war economic miracle, we can see that Japan has positively impacted all the asean economies that are evident today. Japan has more trade with these countries than the US and Europe, thus making a great commitment to fostering multilateral relations, thereby distributing its dependencies and exports to various actors. Although it plays an economic role, by fostering diversification of imports, it at the same time prevents a self-defence mechanism by distancing itself with caution from relying on a single country.

While dealing with these deals with ASEAN, Japan does not cease to establish trade relations with China, and it is explicitly stated in *the Diplomatic Bluebook* of 2019 that the Japan-China bilateral relationship is the most important. In this sense, the U.S. approach often only fosters China's economic isolation, strengthening the argument that Japan's role in appeasing Indo-Pacific tensions diverges from a dichotomic reality of the conflicts between Washington and Beijing. Japan wants to continue to assume the intermediary role between the two superpowers while cultivating regional ties with emerging regional economies.

CONCLUSIONS

Tokyo's attempts to maintain the balance between the two superpowers have their obstacles and complex the problem at hand. The Secretary General of the *Liberal Democratic Party* (LDP), Keitaro Ohno, described relations between China and Japan as "... face to face, we are alike, but under the table we kick each other" (11). This reality shows us that the attempt to balance relations on the diplomatic side is working perfectly, but there is another component that prevents *political goodwill and the highest level of track-one diplomacy* from functioning at the levels it should. While there is no doubt that peace in the region needs to cooperate with China and the other actors, there is always the human side that fears that by allowing China to continue its growth, it will be inevitable that it will conflict to reach its interests.

However, Japan continues to have its own characteristics that allow us to maintain balance in the region through all its ties with the countries of the region, especially ASEAN members, although there are obstacles in relations due to its historical past that it shares with the other countries in the region. Another focus of investment on the part of Japan is to extend investment to African countries with initiatives such as *the Asia-Africa Growth Corridor* (AAGC) that contribute to the balance of investments in Africa by distributing the African continent's focus of Chinese bilateral support that tends to have no intention of stumours of sustainable development in the region. The quality of Japanese investments, although more expensive, tend to have higher quality than investments in Chinese infrastructure.

These corridors are essential in the FOIP strategy, allowing for greater movement of goods and diversification of hypotheses, thus reducing the dependence of several countries on China. These corridors are extremely important for Japan's permanence as an economic power in the region. One of the major obstacles to the success of this strategy is the lack of military patrol vessels in order to prevent violations of border territories and piracy attacks in the region. In 2018, there were some 57 armed attacks on fleets in the Indo Pacific region (12) constituting a major obstacle to good trade practices in the region. It is also added the constant territorial disputes of island territories that further distance the FOIP project.

RECOMENDATIONS

The complex problem of the implementation of the FOIP project is the establishment of a safe space that allows regional and interregional trade to diversify China's economies and dependence, without hindering Beijing's growth. By placing the U.S. as leaders in a development of a space that is hostile to the Chinese

government, it will certainly cause a breach in security and asian and global markets. Japan presents itself as a solution that diverges from the direct conflict between both superpowers, valuing the impact that Japan has on regional countries. Cooperation between the ASEAN countries and the emerging economies of Africa and the Middle East will contribute to peaceful cooperation involving China in the markets and ease the tensions that are increasingly approaching a military conflict.

Japan thus has the capacity to be able to balance the region's relations by developing cooperation agreements with the USA, Europe and the countries of the region in order to establish FOIP and consequently stability in the region (13). In a careful manner, this development must remain free of hostility towards China in order to achieve an improvement in bilateral and multilateral relations of all the countries involved. The safety and maintenance of corridors must be ensured in such a way as not to impede growth in China by entering into an agreement with the Countries of the Asia-Pacific, but also in the Middle East and Africa. This growth must be done in a sustainable way and without a decrease in the quality of support and investment in order to ensure the confidence of all stakeholders who have certainly supported an initiative that will enable them to obtain more resources for their own development.

FOIP should be seen only as a form of development in the region and not a way to contain or impede China's growth. Achieving a structure that calls for cooperation between all, and not *naively*, we are moving towards a decrease in tensions in the region.

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